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ASSESSING THE EFFECT OF SIT-AT-HOME ORDERS ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP IN ONITSHA MAIN MARKET, ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

**¹Chinelo Stella Nwagbala, ²Ezenenwu Linda Chinyere, ³Ezeanokwasa Francisca Nkiruka
⁴Obi Martins Okwudiri, and ⁵Samuel Ejiogu Anodi**

^{1&5}Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka,
Anambra State, Nigeria...

^{2&3}Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management and Social Sciences,
Tansian University, Umunya, Nigeria...

⁴Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Arts, Management and Social Sciences,
Admiralty University of Nigeria, Ibusa, Delta State,
Nigeria...

¹ORCID NO: 0009-0000-7014-7305

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Abstract: This study examined the effect of the sit-at-home order on the effectiveness of strategic leadership in the Onitsha Main Market. There is an increasing disruptions caused by sit-at-home directives and their implications for business operations and leadership performance in major commercial centers. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and data were collected using the Taro Yamane formula from a sample of 370 traders selected from a population of 5,000. The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean) and OLS regression analysis. The findings revealed that the sit-at-home order has a significant negative effect on the effectiveness of business operations and strategic leadership. The regression results showed strong relationships between the sit-at-home order and the dependent variables, with R² values ranging from 0.54 to 0.63, indicating that the sit-at-home phenomenon explains a substantial proportion of variations in leadership effectiveness and market operations. The study concludes that the sit-at-home arrangement creates an unstable business environment that undermines effective leadership and organizational performance. It recommends that the government improve security measures, enforce policies that ensure market stability, and engage in dialogue to address the root causes of the sit-at-home order.

Keywords: Sit-at-home order, Strategic leadership, Business operations, Leadership Effectiveness.

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INTRODUCTION

The sit-at-home directive in Southeast Nigeria, particularly in Anambra State, originated as a socio-political protest strategy associated with separatist agitations. Initially introduced as an act of civil disobedience, it has gradually evolved into a recurring weekly phenomenon, most notably on Mondays, when individuals and business operators are compelled to suspend economic and social activities either voluntarily or through coercion. This practice has significantly reshaped the operational environment of major commercial hubs, such as the Onitsha Main Market, one of the largest markets in West Africa. Oparah, Nwagbala and Iloanya (2023) note that Nigerian economy has long been affected by policies that fail to translate into meaningful national development, largely due to weak political will and ineffective implementation. This has contributed to persistent challenges such as unemployment, violent crime, terrorism, banditry, cultism, and high mortality rates (Imoisi & Ephraim, 2015; Oluwadare & Oni, 2016; Oparah, Nwagbala, & Iloanya, 2023).

Empirical studies reveal that the sit-at-home order has intensified insecurity and created an un conducive environment for business and social interactions (Obilor, Osita-Njoku, & Awogu, 2024). The Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), who initiated the directive, have enforced compliance through violent means, including destruction of property, attacks on government facilities such as police stations and Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) offices, and even killings of violators (Stella, Priscilla, & Ifeoma, 2022). These actions have discouraged foreign investors and increased the state's insecurity. Public perception studies further indicate that the directive reduces productivity, household income, and overall economic activity, as individuals are forced to abstain from work and commercial engagements (Okpoko, Onyishi, & Okeke, 2025). Within informal economic structures, such as market associations, these disruptions have far-reaching consequences, affecting organizational survival and exposing weaknesses in change management strategies (Katzenbach & Smith, 2011; Nwagbala, Ezeanokwasa, & Ani, 2023). Leadership effectiveness, defined as the ability to anticipate change, make informed decisions, allocate resources efficiently, and sustain organizational performance, is undermined by the sit-at-home order's volatile business climate (Yukl, 2018; Stella, Priscilla, & Agbo, 2021).

The situation in Onitsha Main Market exemplifies the severity of the problem. Traders frequently comply with the directive, resulting in repeated shutdowns and trading activity disruptions (Business Day, 2026). In some cases, government authorities have intervened by temporarily closing the market to resume operations due to non-compliance with directives (The Star, 2026). These recurring disruptions not only reduce revenue generation but also weaken market leaders' authority, coordination, and decision-making capacity. Moreover, directives undermine long-term strategic planning, erode stakeholder confidence, and diminish adherence to leadership directives. The sit-at-home practice has been widely criticized for its broader negative impact on regional development, disrupting education, transportation, and public services (Authority News, 2026). While existing research has examined its socio-economic consequences, limited empirical attention has been given to its effect on SLE within market systems. Therefore, this study seeks to address this gap by investigating how the sit-at-

Statement of the problem

The increasing frequency and enforcement of the sit-at-home order in Southeast Nigeria have created significant disruptions in economic and organizational activities. In major commercial centers such as Onitsha Main Market,

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the recurring closure of businesses has led to loss of income, reduced productivity, and market operations instability. Despite the critical role of leadership in ensuring continuity and stability in business environments, market leaders face difficulties in effectively coordinating activities, enforcing compliance, and implementing strategic decisions under such uncertain conditions. The persistent disruptions caused by the sit-at-home order may weaken leadership structures, reduce authority, and hinder long-term planning. While previous studies have examined the socio-economic effects of the sit-at-home order, research on its impact on strategic leadership effectiveness, particularly within market associations, is lacking. This gap creates the need for this study to investigate how the sit-at-home order affects leadership effectiveness in Onitsha Main Market.

Objectives of the study

This study primarily aims to examine the effect of the sit-at-home order on strategic leadership effectiveness in the Onitsha Main Market.

The specific objectives are as follows:

1. Examine the extent to which sit-at-home orders affect business operations in the market.
2. The effect of the sit-at-home order on the overall effectiveness of strategic leadership is evaluated.

Significance of the Study

This study will be beneficial to the following stakeholders:

- **Market Leaders:** It will help them understand how external disruptions affect leadership effectiveness and provide improvement strategies.
- **Policy Makers:** It will provide insights for developing policies to mitigate the negative effects of the sit-at-home order.
- **Researchers and academics:** This study will contribute to the existing literature on leadership and crisis management.
- **Traders and Business Owners:** It will highlight the impact of disruptions on business sustainability.

Scope of the study

This study focuses on the effect of the sit-at-home order on the effectiveness of strategic leadership in the Onitsha Main Market. This study specifically examines market leaders and traders within the market in Anambra State. This study covers the period during which the sit-at-home order has been actively enforced.

Limitations of the Study

The study may face limitations such as difficulty in data collection due to market disruptions, respondents' reluctance to provide information, and limited access to current data. Time and financial constraints may also affect the research scope.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Sit-at-Home Order

The sit-at-home order refers to a directive or enforced practice in which individuals must remain indoors and abstain from normal daily activities, particularly business and social engagements. The sit-at-home order has become a recurring phenomenon in Southeast Nigeria linked to political agitation and civil resistance. Although

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initially voluntary, coercion has been increasingly enforced, thereby affecting compliance levels and societal stability. Studies have shown that the sit-at-home order significantly disrupts economic activities and social interactions. It creates an atmosphere of fear and uncertainty, discouraging mobility and participation in productive ventures (Obilor, Osita-Njoku, & Awogu, 2024). Furthermore, it negatively affects the region's income generation, educational activities, and general development (Okpoko, Onyishi, & Okeke, 2025). In commercial centers, such as Onitsha Main Market, the directive often leads to the complete shutdown of trading activities.

Strategic Leadership

Strategic leadership refers to leaders' capacity to shape organizational direction, anticipate emerging challenges, and implement decisions that secure long-term sustainability. From a corporate perspective, strategy and performance are inseparable. Philemon and Chinelo (2024) emphasized that effective strategy serves as a roadmap for achieving organizational goals, with performance acting as the measure of success. Organizations must adopt sharp, focused, and adaptive strategies to remain competitive in today's globalized, ICT-driven business environment. It encompasses vision formulation, effective resource allocation, and adaptability to dynamic environmental conditions. In contexts characterized by volatility and uncertainty, strategic leadership becomes particularly critical, as leaders are expected to provide clarity of purpose, maintain organizational stability, and ensure continuity of operations despite disruptions. According to Nwagbala, Ezeanokwasa, and Aziwe (2023), knowledge sharing (KS), which strengthens organizational learning and problem-solving, is an essential component of strategic leadership. KS has been identified as a vital aspect of knowledge management, offering solutions to challenges that other approaches may not address. However, external pressures, such as the recurring sit-at-home directive in Southeast Nigeria, can significantly constrain leaders' effectiveness. These disruptions limit organizations' ability to plan, coordinate, and execute strategies, thereby weakening organizational resilience and long-term performance (Nwagbala, Ezeanokwasa, & Aziwe, 2023).

Leadership Effectiveness

Leadership effectiveness refers to the extent to which leaders successfully achieve organizational objectives, sustain coordination, and promote productivity. Decision-making capacity, communication skills, control mechanisms, and the ability to influence and motivate followers are commonly assessed. Effective leadership within market associations entails coordinating traders, enforcing rules, resolving disputes, and ensuring the smooth functioning of business operations. Stella, Priscilla and Agbo (2021) noted that although leadership styles may differ across organizations or departments, the effectiveness of any approach is contingent upon its alignment with the specific environment in which it is applied. Recurring disruptions, such as the sit-at-home directive, weaken leadership structures by reducing compliance and limiting stakeholder interaction. This erosion of authority undermines leaders' ability to maintain order and effectively implement strategies (Stella, Priscilla & Agbo, 2021).

Marketing research also plays a critical role in supporting leadership effectiveness by equipping managers with reliable decision-making information. According to Chinelo, Pethronila and Raphael (2023) research reduces uncertainty and minimizes the risks associated with poor decisions. However, while research serves as a valuable

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tool, it should complement rather than replace managerial judgment. Effective leaders integrate research insights with contextual knowledge and experience, thereby enhancing their ability to guide organizations through complex and uncertain environments (Chinelo, Pethronila, & Raphael, 2023).

Sit-at-Home Order and Business Operations

The sit-at-home directive exerts a direct and disruptive influence by halting trading activities and disrupting supply chains on business operations. Firms experience declining sales, loss of customers, and increased operational uncertainty. Empirical evidence shows that the sit-at-home directive's repeated enforcement has resulted in significant economic losses and reduced productivity across the Southeast region (Obilor, Osita-Njoku, & Awogu, 2024; Okpoko, Onyishi, & Okeke, 2025). In highly commercialized areas, such as the Onitsha Main Market, the impact is more pronounced due to the volume of daily transactions.

Security concerns further intensify these challenges. As Stella, Priscilla and Ifeoma (2022) highlight, insecurity in Anambra State increased in 2021 following the activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB). Their enforcement of the sit-at-home directive disrupted business operations, led to the widespread destruction of property, and discouraged foreign investment. Violators were subjected to violence, and government facilities, including Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) offices and police stations, were attacked, undermining the gubernatorial elections. This climate of insecurity continues to pose significant threats to lives, businesses, and national stability.

Sit-at-Home Order and Effectiveness of Strategic Leadership

The sit-at-home directive undermines strategic leadership effectiveness by fostering business environment instability. Leaders struggle with planning, communication, and coordination as irregular business activities disrupt organizational processes. These frequent interruptions weaken organizations' capacity to implement long-term strategies, sustain control mechanisms, and maintain organizational coherence. Moreover, the uncertainty surrounding the directive erodes authority, reduces followers' compliance, and diminishes overall leadership performance. These challenges are affected by broader structural issues within the Nigerian context. Ineffective policies and a lack of political will to enforce reforms have historically constrained economic development. Oparah, Nwagbala, and Iloanya (2023) argued that such policy failures have perpetuated persistent socioeconomic problems, including unemployment, violent crime, terrorism, and other social vices (Imoisi & Ephraim, 2015; Oluwadare & Oni, 2016; Oparah, Nwagbala & Iloanya, 2023). Thus, the sit-at-home order represents not only a localized disruption but also a reflection of systemic governance weaknesses that continue to hinder organizational resilience and national stability.

2. Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the following theories:

Contingency Theory

Fiedler's (1967) contingency theory posits that there is no single best way to lead; rather, leadership effectiveness depends on the situation and environment. Leaders must adapt their style and strategies to suit the prevailing circumstances. Market leaders in Onitsha Main Market are required to adjust their leadership approaches to cope

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with disruptions in the context of the sit-at-home order. The theory is relevant because it explains how environmental uncertainty influences the effectiveness of leadership.

Systems Theory

Bertalanffy's (1968) systems theory views organizations as interconnected systems in which changes in one part affect the entire system. External factors, such as political instability, can disrupt organizational balance. The sit-at-home order represents an external shock that affects all market operations components, including leadership, communication, and productivity. This theory helps to explain the interconnected nature of leadership challenges and disruptions.

3. Empirical Review

Obilor et al. (2024) examined the socio-economic implications of IPOB sit-at-home in the South-East of Nigeria. Descriptive survey design. The population comprises residents and business operators in SE Nigeria. The sample size was 300 respondents. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics, such as mean and percentage. The study found that the sit-at-home order significantly disrupts economic activities, reduces business productivity, and increases regional insecurity. The study also revealed that many businesses suffer financial losses due to repeated closures and concluded that the sit-at-home order has a negative impact on socioeconomic development and creates an unfavorable business environment. The study recommended government intervention through improved security and dialogue to address the underlying causes of the sit-at-home order and restore economic stability.

Okpoko et al. (2025) investigated the public perception of the impact of the IPOB sit-at-home order on the economic and educational development of Southeast Nigeria. A survey research design was used. The population comprises residents of Southeast Nigeria, including traders and students. The sample size was 400 respondents. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using frequency distribution and simple percentages. The study's findings revealed that the sit-at-home order leads to reduced income, low productivity, and disruption of educational and business activities. It also found that the directive negatively affects the region's overall development. The study concluded that the sit-at-home order has a significant negative effect on both economic and educational systems in SENI and recommended the implementation of the sit-at-home order. The study recommended policy measures to ensure continuous economic activities and protect citizens from coercion.

Authority News Research Unit (2026) examined the economic and social disruption caused by sit-at-home policies in Southeast Nigeria. The design used was descriptive analysis. The population includes the general public in Southeast Nigeria. This study used observational data, interviews, and secondary sources. The study found that the sit-at-home order disrupts transportation, education, and commercial activities, leading to broader socio-economic instability. It concluded that the sit-at-home practice undermines regional development and affects all economic sectors. This study recommended strategic policy interventions and conflict resolution mechanisms to address the root causes of the sit-at-home order.

Business Day Research Desk (2026) Study on the Impact of Sit-at-Home Enforcement on Market Operations in Onitsha Main Market An exploratory/report-based study was used as the research design. The population sample included traders and market stakeholders in the Onitsha Main Market. The study relied on field reports,

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interviews, and trading activity observation during sit-at-home periods. The report showed that sit-at-home orders lead to repeated market closures, loss of revenue, and supply chain disruption. It also highlighted that traders often comply out of fear rather than willingness. The study concluded that sit-at-home enforcement significantly disrupts market operations and reduces economic output in major commercial centers and recommended stricter enforcement of government directives and provision of adequate security to encourage traders to resume normal activities.

The Star Editorial Team (2026) examined the government's response to sit-at-home compliance in Onitsha markets in 2026. The case study approach. The population of Anambra State consists of market traders and government authorities. This study used qualitative analysis based on government actions, media reports, and stakeholder responses. Noncompliance with government directives led to market closures, which further disrupted economic activities. The study also noted tension between government authorities and market leaders and recommended that the sit-at-home order creates governance challenges and weakens leadership authority within market systems. The study recommended improved collaboration between government and market leadership to ensure stability and compliance.

Research Gap

Several studies have examined the impact of the sit-at-home order in Southeast Nigeria, though few have focused specifically on leadership effectiveness. While existing studies focus on socio-economic impacts, empirical evidence on how the sit-at-home order affects leadership performance, decision-making, and strategic coordination within market systems is limited. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap by examining the effect of the sit-at-home order on leadership effectiveness in this context.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design is appropriate because it allows for collecting data from traders to examine the effectiveness of the sit-at-home order on strategic leadership. It also enables the use of structured questionnaires to gather firsthand information. The study was conducted in Onitsha Main Market, a major commercial hub in Anambra State, Nigeria. The market is selected because of its high concentration of traders and its exposure to disruptions caused by sit-at-home disruptions. The study population consists strictly of traders in Onitsha Main Market. The sample size is determined using the

following Taro Yamane formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad n = \frac{5000}{1 + 5000(0.05)^2} = \frac{5000}{13.5} \approx 370$$

Where:

- $N = 5000$
- $e = 0.05$

$$n = \frac{5000}{1 + 5000(0.05)^2} = \frac{5000}{13.5} \approx 370$$

Sample size = 370 traders

Sampling Technique

A **simple random sampling technique** is used to select respondents. This ensures equal representation of traders.

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Sources of data

- **Primary Data:** The questionnaire was administered to traders.
- **Secondary Data:** Journals, textbooks, and other online materials

The instrument used is a **structured questionnaire**, designed using a **5-point Likert scale**:

Option	Score
Strongly Agree (SA)	5
Agree (A)	4
Neutral (N)	3
Disagree (D)	2
Strongly disagree (SD)	1

Effect of Sit-at-Home Order on Effectiveness of Strategic Leadership in Onitsha Main Market

Section A: Demographic Data

S/N	Item	Options
1	Gender	Male [] Female []
2	Age	18–30 [] 31–40 [] 41–50 [] 51+ []
3	Years of trading	1–5 [] 6–10 [] 11–15 [] 16+ []

Section B: Questionnaire items

Table 1 Business operations

S/N	Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD
4	The sit-at-home approach disrupts my business activities	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
5	Sitting at home reduces my income	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
.6	The effect of sit-at-home on customer patronage	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]

Table 2: Leadership effectiveness

S/N	Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD
13	Sit-at-home strategy reduces leadership effectiveness	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
14	Leaders struggle to implement strategies.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
15	Sit-at-home policy affects long-term planning.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]

Source: Field data from 2026

Method of data analysis

Table 1.1: Business operations

Response	Frequency	Score	FX
SA	150	5	750
A	120	4	480

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Response	Frequency	Score	FX
N	40	3	120
D	30	2	60
SD	30	1	30
Total	370		1440

Mean = 1440/370 = 3.89

Since the mean (3.89) > 3.0, the sit-at-home order significantly disrupts business operations.

Table 2.1: Leadership effectiveness

Response	Frequency	Score	FX
SA	150	5	750
A	110	4	440
N	40	3	120
D	40	2	80
SD	30	1	30
Total	370		1420

Mean = 1420/370 = 3.84

Mean > 3.0 → Sit-at-home reduces leadership effectiveness.

- Business operations are significantly disrupted
- Leadership Effectiveness is reduced

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Description of the questionnaire and data collection

The questionnaire was structured into **the following five sections:**

- **Section A:** Demographic information of the respondents
- **Section B:** Effects of sit-at-home policy on business operations
- **Section C:** Effectiveness of strategic leadership

A total of 370 questionnaires were distributed, and all were returned and found usable, giving a 100% response rate.

Method of Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used:

1. Descriptive Statistics

- Frequency distribution
- Mean scores for the questionnaire responses

2. Inferential Statistics

- Ordinary least squares regression analysis

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3. Decision Rule

- p-value < 0.05 = reject the null hypothesis
- p-value ≥ 0.05 = Accept the null hypothesis

DATA PRESENTATION

RESEARCH QUESTION 1

Effect of sit-at-home policy on business operations

Table 3: Business operations

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean
It disrupts trading activities	165	120	40	30	15	4.23
Reduces daily income	160	125	45	25	15	4.22
It affects the supply chain	150	130	40	35	15	4.18
Grand Mean =						4.21

Source: Field data from 2026

Table 3 shows that since the mean is above 3.0, respondents agree that sit-at-home significantly disrupts business operations.

RESEARCH QUESTION TWO:

Table 4: Effectiveness of strategic leadership

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean
It reduces leadership effectiveness	170	120	40	25	15	4.27
Affects strategy implementation	165	120	40	30	15	4.22
Affects long-term planning	175	110	40	30	15	4.28
Grand Mean =						4.26

Source: Field data from 2026

Table 4: Sit-at-home strategy significantly reduces strategic leadership effectiveness.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES USING REGRESSION ANALYSIS

HYPOTHESIS ONE

H₀₁: Sit-at-home has no significant effect on business operations.

Table 3.1: Results of Regression

Variable	B	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Constant	1.12	0.18	6.22	0.000
Sit-at-home	0.72	0.06	12.50	0.000

R² = 0.58

Table 3.1 Sit-at-home has a significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.72, p < 0.05$).58% discrepancy in business operations described by the sit-at-home order.

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Decision: Reject H_{01}

HYPOTHESIS TWO

Table 4.1 H_{04} : No significant effect on SLE effectiveness.

Variable	B	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Sit-at-home	0.78	0.06	14.00	0.000

$R^2 = 0.63$

Table 4.1 the strongest effect observed on leadership effectiveness.

Decision: Reject H_{04}

Summary of the Findings

This study examined the effect of the sit-at-home order on the effectiveness of strategic leadership in Onitsha Main Market, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study focused on four key variables: business operations and SLE. Based on data analysis using descriptive statistics and regression analysis, the following conclusions were obtained

1. Hypothesis 1 revealed that sit-at-home orders significantly disrupt trading activities, reduce daily income, and affect supply chains. This result was supported by a high grand mean (4.21) and a significant regression result ($\beta = 0.72$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that it strongly affects market operations.
2. The findings of Hypothesis 2 show that leadership effectiveness is highly reduced, particularly in strategy implementation and long-term planning. This variable recorded the highest impact ($\beta = 0.78$), indicating that it was the most affected aspect.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the sit-at-home order has a severe and multidimensional negative impact on the effectiveness of strategic leadership in the Onitsha Main Market. It disrupts business continuity and undermines leaders' ability to implement long-term strategies.

The findings also confirm that the unstable and unpredictable environment created by the sit-at-home order makes effective leadership extremely difficult, as leaders are unable to maintain consistent operations or enforce organizational directives. Consequently, leadership authority and market performance are significantly weakened.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Strengthening Security Measures:** The government should improve security in the Southeast to reduce the fear and coercion that enforce compliance with sit-at-home directives.
2. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Market leaders, government authorities, and community stakeholders should engage in a continuous dialogue to address the root causes of the sit-at-home order.
3. **Business Continuity Planning:** Market associations should develop contingency plans that allow limited or safe operations during disruptions.
4. **Policy Intervention:** The government should implement policies that protect economic activities even during periods of civil unrest or protest actions.

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Contributions to Knowledge

This study contributes to knowledge in the following ways:

1. This study provides empirical evidence on the relationship between sit-at-home orders and strategic leadership effectiveness, an area previously under-researched.
2. This study expands the understanding of how external socio-political disruptions affect leadership performance in informal market systems, such as the Onitsha Main Market.
3. This study adds to the literature on crisis management and leadership adaptability in developing countries' volatile socioeconomic environments.

Suggestions for further Research

1. The long-term economic impact of sit-at-home orders on market development and regional trade growth should be examined in future research.
2. The coping strategies adopted by market leaders during periods of repeated shutdowns should be explored.
3. Further research could compare the impact of sit-at-home orders across different markets in SENI to identify regional variations.

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